

Are Vegetation Indices Really so Different: an Unsupervised Perspective

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Abstract

Remote sensing has been employed to gather rapidly dynamic, non-destructive information on crops and has been utilized across numerous fields. The information richness has been condensed into a plurality of vegetation indices. They offer quantitative data about crop growth and health, supporting a range of precision agriculture practices. The introduction of many indices has been motivated by particular problems unsolved by the previous list. In this paper we investigate if these indices are indeed so different and to quantify the differences among them we assume an unsupervised approach. We focus our study on a PRISMA image from Brașov area. Out of this image, we select four semantic areas indicating agricultural crop, forest, alpine pasture and urban setting and into these four cases we evaluate differences between the most used vegetation index, NDVI, and other several popular choices. The differences are quantified from a statistic viewpoint, using Pearson and Spearman correlation coefficients and from an image consistency, using SSIM. We show that conditioned on semantic category, significant differences arise.

Keywords— remote sensing, vegetation indices, correlation, structural similarity

1 Introduction

The World Summit on Food Security predicted that in 25 years, “The world’s population is expected to grow to almost 10 billion by 2050, boosting agricultural demand, in a scenario of modest economic growth, by some 50 percent compared to 2013”. Yet, this rise in food production must be paired with sustainable management of agricultural lands to prevent or mitigate the negative impacts on water and soil quality, land degradation, greenhouse gas emissions, and biodiversity [1]. Given the challenging context for agriculture, there is a pressing need to monitor crop growth and status across various locations and environmental settings, with diverse temporal resolutions, and for multiple purposes. Furthermore, the purpose of maintaining biodiversity, requires that not only agricultural land to be monitored, but, also, naturally vegetated and even urban landscapes. A solution for the holistic monitoring of all these is offered by remote sensing via satellite or drone imaging.

Remote sensing supports various precision agriculture practices (e.g. seeding, fertilization, protection, and cultivation), by offering insights into crop growth and health,

soil conditions, and environmental factors [2]. Remote sensing involves acquiring information about an object or phenomenon from a distance using an instrument or sensor mounted on a platform, such as a satellite, aircraft, UAV/UGV, or probe. The sensor measures electromagnetic radiation reflected or emitted by the target. The resulting information depends on the specific properties of the instrument and its platform, including satellite orbitography, UAV/UGV motion plan, field sensor position and orientation, active or passive sensing, detector array and optical lens characteristics, and storage capabilities [2]. These properties determine the spectral, directional, and polarization capabilities, spatial resolution, revisit frequencies, and signal-to-noise ratio. With respect to platforms, satellite-based remote sensing offers increasing spatial, spectral and temporal resolution, enabling the extraction of long-term data series that are consistent, comparable, and cost-effective [3]. Moreover, some satellite platforms, like Sentinel 2, Landsat 7-8, PRISMA provide free access to visible and multi(hyper) spectral data.

The core observation is that vegetation canopy, depending on the development stage, health, etc. responds differently to various ranges of electromagnetic waves from satellite acquired data, wthat are well beyond visible spectrum. Thus, the main applications for remote sensing of vegetation utilizes the following light spectra [4]:

- the ultraviolet (UV) from 10 to 380 nm;
- the visible (VIS) spectra, going from blue (450-495 nm), through green (495-570 nm), towards red (620-750 nm) wavelength and
- the near and mid-infrared band (850-1700 nm) - NIR.

One satellite example is PRISMA (PRecursores IperSpettrale della Missione Applicativa) [5], which resulted as a space mission equipped with an advanced hyperspectral sensor, along with pre-operational activities via a companion mission control and data processing ground segment. Its performance has been optimized for the entire European and Mediterranean region, predicting daily imaging of areas exceeding 100,000 km^2 . PRISMA imaging includes the generation (archiving, cataloging, cloud cover assessment, and quick looks) and distribution of all data received each day. Additionally, it involves processing at least 30 hyperspectral scenes (each 30 km by 30 km) to level 2d (geocoded over terrain).

Hyperspectral satellite imaging offer a wide amount of information. To deal with this richness, vegetation indices have been proposed and developed. They are computed from various ranges light spectra (mainly from NIR and VIS, but not limited to) and emphasize various plant characteristics such as growth and vigor, water content, pigments, sugar and carbohydrate levels, protein content, and aromatic compounds [6]. Practical applications of vegetation indices use the reflectivity peaks or overtones of specific components of the visible and near/mid-infrared regions [3].

While a very wide set of vegetation indices (VI) have been proposed [7], the most used is the normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI). In this paper we seek to investigate and quantify differences between other popular VIs and NDVI. The approach is dual: statistically and from an imaging point of view. We focus on an area that offers a diverse landscape such as Braşov area; we define semantic (i.e. terrain) categories: alpine pasture, forest, urban and agricultural crops. We measure the differences using the standard euclidean distance and respectively two correlation coefficients (Pearson and Spearman). Since VIs are often used to construct images, we also quantify differences using a standard image quality metric namely the structural similarity index measure (SSIM).

Prior works. Following the wide plethora of developed applications that are based on vegetation indices, there are many VI variants, having more thorough or vague definitions. For a compressed presentation, we take the prevalent practice and refer to them by their acronym. For more details, we kindly point the reader to the integrative work of Radovcaj et al. [7].

Comparative analysis of vegetation indices has been conducted previously and they focused on quantitative and qualitative differences. For instance, Payero et al. [8] evaluated 11 VIs based on their correlation with plant height for alfalfa and grass, finding at least medium correlation for all indices and strong correlation for variations of VIs such as Band Ratio (RATIO), TVI, NDVI, and IPVI. Similarly, Cao et al. [9] utilized different satellites and corresponding images of a mountain to investigate differences in gamut and accuracy, discovering that under those conditions, that SAVI and VIUPD range has higher upper bound than NDVI.

Vegetation indices are mostly about green canopy and thus establishing their capability to predict green leaf area has been emphasized in previous works. Vina et al. [10] examined the physical and chemical backgrounds of various indices to rank their performance. Towers et al. [11] quantified the differences in the accuracy of leaf canopy measurements among several indices for vineyards. For that specific scenario, involving linear and logarithmic regression, NDVI was found to be the most accurate, while SAVI2 was identified as the best indicator of leaf area.

Other works started with an initial comparison, noted limitations (especially in NDVI) and proposed alleviating formulas. For instance Wu et al. [12] indicated better use of GNDVI for dryland. Xie et al. [13] proposed a combination of existing indices as a better alternative than LAI in estimating leaf area.

In summary, while comparative analysis has been carried, they had refer to particular problems and it is not clear if their conclusion extends beyond the limiting assumptions. Furthermore, the comparison was carried by direct analysis of peaks and ranges, while similarities have been evaluated in terms of linear (i.e. Pearson) correlation only. We used a wider set of measures, by incorporating non-linearity (due to using Spearman coefficient) and measure the similarity of the resulting images.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 presents the data used in the experiments, the envisaged vegetation indices and the metrics used to emphasize differences between VIs. Section 3 presents results and comments. The paper ends with discussion and conclusions.

2 Method and materials

In this work, we have used five vegetation indices that are computed on PRISMA image. The most popular, NDVI, which is a measurement of a green and healthy vegetation, forms also the basis of the experiments as other four indices are compared to it. The other indices that were used in this project are VARI, GNDVI, ARVI, LAI [7].

2.1 Data

In this article, we analyzed a PRISMA hyperspectral image captured on March 24, 2023, over the Braşov region in Romania. The image was produced by the HYP/Pan module from PRISMA. This instrument combines a hyperspectral camera operating in the 0.4 - 2.5 μm spectral range (covering both VNIR and SWIR channels with an overlap from 920nm to 1010nm for precise reconstruction of each pixel's spectral signature) and a panchromatic camera capturing images in the 0.4 - 0.7 μm spectral range [5]. This setup achieves an average spectral resolution of less than 10nm across the entire spectral span, generating over 200 spectrally distinct bands with an accuracy of ± 0.1 nm. The spatial resolution is 30 meters, and the full image size is 1000 x 1000 pixels, covering an area of 30 \times 30 kilometers.

The image, rendered in RGB colorspace, may be seen in the Figure 1. As one can notice, the Braşov region is diverse, gathering in the photographed area a wide variety of geographical features: in the low-right corner is the Postăvaru massif (top

Figure 1: The Prisma image over the Braşov area, centered, approximately, at $45^{\circ}40'N$, $25^{\circ}31'E$, with selected areas marked.

altitude 1799m), mostly covered with coniferous and beech forest, that in the upper part has high altitude pasture; in the low left, there are the relatively low-lying Perşani mountains (culminating at 1292m), in the center-to-right is the Braşov city while the upper half is the Țara Bârsei depression, a relatively flat area with altitude between 500 and 600, that is suitable for agricultural crop. The crop ranges from wheat, corn to potato and sugar beet. Out of this image, we manually selected 4 areas, that are also marked on the image and contain alpine pasture, forest, urban and agricultural crop.

2.2 Vegetation Indices

Given the hyperspectral PRISMA image, several vegetation indices, starting with the most used, NDVI, have been computed using the following formulas:

1. Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

$$\text{NDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Red}} \quad (1)$$

2. Visible Atmospherically Resistant Index (VARI)

$$\text{VARI} = \frac{\text{Green} - \text{Red}}{\text{Green} + \text{Red} - \text{Blue}} \quad (2)$$

3. Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (GNDVI)

$$\text{GNDVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Green}}{\text{NIR} + \text{Green}} \quad (3)$$

4. Atmospherically Resistant Vegetation Index (ARVI)

$$\text{ARVI} = \frac{\text{NIR} - (\text{Red} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))}{\text{NIR} + (\text{Red} - \gamma(\text{Blue} - \text{Red}))} \quad (4)$$

where $\gamma = 1.7$.

Figure 2: The images, represented as heatmaps, for the vegetation indices selected and respectively for the four types of landscape. One might note the differences between images of the same location.

5. Leaf Area Index (LAI) using Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI)

$$\text{EVI} = 2.5 \times \frac{\text{NIR} - \text{Red}}{\text{NIR} + 6 \times \text{Red} - 7.5 \times \text{Blue} + 1}$$

$$\text{LAI} = 3.618 \times \text{EVI} - 0.118 \quad (5)$$

The images for each vegetation index and respectively for the four types of landscape can be seen in Figure 2.

2.3 Statistical and Imaging Similarity

In this approach, we considered that the NDI measurements being the reference measure and denoted, for pixel i by, x_i . The other VIs (sequentially one of VARI, GNDVI, ARVI, LAI) are denoted by y_i . The similarities between the two indices are measured by:

Euclidean **L2 distance**.

$$L2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \sum_i (x_i - y_i)^2 \quad (6)$$

The interpretation of L2 is straightforward: small values indicate small differences and large, otherwise.

Pearson correlation coefficient.

$$\rho_P(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{\sum_i ((x_i - E[x_i])(y_i - E[y_i]))}{\sqrt{\sum_i (x_i - E[x_i])^2} \sqrt{\sum_i (y_i - E[y_i])^2}}, \quad (7)$$

where $E[\cdot]$ is the mean.

This coefficient measures the *linear* correlation of the two variables: if \mathbf{y} is linearly approximated by \mathbf{x} , then $|\rho_P| \rightarrow 1$, otherwise; for weak approximation $|\rho_P| \rightarrow 0$. If $\rho_P < 0$, the best linear approximation is negative: when \mathbf{y} increases, \mathbf{x} decreases.

Spearman rank correlation coefficient. To compute it, the two variables are turned into rank variables $\mathbf{x} \rightarrow R(\mathbf{x})$: each set is ordered and the value is replaced by the rank in the respective set. Then, Spearman rank coefficient is the Pearson correlation coefficient of the rank variables

$$\rho_S(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \rho_P(R(\mathbf{x}), R(\mathbf{y})) \quad (8)$$

A derived formula is, thus:

$$\rho_S(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = 1 - \frac{6 \sum_i d_i^2}{n(n^2 - 1)}, \quad (9)$$

where d_i is the difference between the ranks of corresponding values x_i and y_i , while n is the number of observations.

The Spearman correlation coefficient measures the linear correlation of the rank, which is if the two variables are related by a *monotonic* (potentially non-linear) function.

Structural similarity index measure (SSIM) [14] is computed over a matrices (2D-images): $\mathbf{x} = \{x_{ij}\}$. Here, the SSIM is computed on small windows, having 11×11 size.

$$SSIM(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = \frac{(2E[\mathbf{x}]E[\mathbf{y}] + C_1)(2\sigma_{xy} + C_2)}{(E[\mathbf{x}]^2 + E[\mathbf{y}]^2 + C_1)(\sigma_x^2 + \sigma_y^2 + C_2)} \quad (10)$$

Where \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{y} are the two windows being compared, σ_x^2 σ_y^2 are their variances. $C_1 = (K_1L)^2$ and $C_2 = (K_2L)^2$ are constants to stabilize the division with weak denominators, with L being the dynamic range of the pixel values (typically $2^{\text{bits per pixel}} - 1$), while $K_1 = 0.01$ and $K_2 = 0.03$ by default.

The SSIM index has values between -1 and 1, where 1 indicates perfect similarity, 0 indicates complete lack of similarity, and -1 indicates perfect anti-correlation. Compared to previous coefficients, being computed on windows, SSIM takes into account the *local context* in the data array.

3 Implementation and results

The evaluation code has been implemented in Python. Obtained results are presented numerically and graphically in Figure 3. Analyzing them, some observations can be made:

(I) There is no general trend, meaning all observations are dependent on the index pair and/or on the terrain.

(II) The VIs are built for agricultural crops and they behave differently if other terrain is considered. L2 distance shows the largest differences for this terrain (agricultural), with NDVI-VARI pair standing out.

(III) LAI-NDVI are highly anti-correlated, NDVI-GNDVI are medium correlated, no matter the terrain. The relation between NDVI and VARI and respectively ARVI is dependent on the terrain and on the linearity sought. The Spearman coefficient reveals a non-linear, weak, relation, that Pearson misses.

(IV) SSIM reveals that the relation between VIs is highly dependent on terrain (vegetation). There is a significantly different behavior between human influenced (i.e urban+agricultural) and natural scenery. While correlation coefficients (Pearson and Spearman) found strong connection between NDVI and GNDVI, SSIM indicates that GNDVI image is perceptually different from the NDVI.

Figure 3: The statistical and imaging similarity of the selected indices with respect to NDVI, for various categories of landscape. Figure is better viewed in digital form, under zoom-in.

4 Conclusions

Discussion. The list of vegetation indices is rich and each is motivated by a specific condition. Quantified by unsupervised statistical measures, their relation is complex, often non-linear and conditioned by the terrain. The similarity, for the same pair, ranges from “zero” to “almost perfect” depending on the measure (which is, by the nature of relation) and on the terrain.

Limitations. The evaluation has been carried in specific conditions: data acquired from PRSIMA satellite, with a specific implicit parameters. The study uses crop from a specific location in Braşov county, Romania, which has implicit conditions about vegetation (plant photographed) and geographical characteristics.

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